

**Exploring Behavior Change Techniques in Virtual Reality-Based Rehabilitation
after Total Knee Arthroplasty: A Scoping Review**

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ABSTRACT

Objective: The main objectives of this review were to provide an overview of research concerning: 1- To explore used Behavior Change Techniques (BCTs) in VR-based intervention. 2-To code and analyze the state of BCTs in VR-based rehabilitation after TKA.

Introduction: Total Knee Arthroplasty (TKA) is recommended to treat advanced-stage knee osteoarthritis (OA). While TKA can alleviate symptoms and improve knee function, most individuals require rehabilitation to aid in their recovery. Advances in immersive technology have led to Virtual Reality (VR) for delivering rehabilitation. Understanding how an intervention works is crucial to assess its effectiveness. Incorporating Behavior Change Techniques (BCTs) is critical to intervention design. This study aimed to investigate the presence of BCTs in eligible studies within this review. Since there was a lack of explicit descriptions of BCTs used in interventions, we employed Felsberg's methodology and Michie's BCTs Taxonomy to identify keywords and establish connections with the BCTs employed.

Inclusion/ Exclusion Criteria: The inclusion criteria specify that participants must be 19 or older, physically stable, without severe medical illnesses, and possess adequate visual and auditory acuity. The review includes randomized controlled trials (RCTs) and non-randomized controlled trials (non-RCTs) published in English between 2010 and 2023, which saw significant advancements in VR technology. Participants with certain conditions, such as claustrophobia or cognitive disorders, are excluded from the study.

Methods: This scoping review was conducted in five stages based on Arksey and O'Malley's framework, including (1) identifying the research question, (2) identifying relevant studies, (3) selecting the studies, (4) charting the data and (5) collating, summarizing, and reporting the results.

Results: 1,455 studies were initially screened from four databases: PubMed, Medline (Ovid), CINAHL, and Embase (Ovid). Following removing duplicated and irrelevant studies, two independent reviewers reviewed the full text of 117 studies, and finally, nine studies of VR-based rehabilitation were included in this scoping review. Most studies did not describe the BCTs used in their methodologies. Concerning BCT, goal setting was used in 55.5% of the studies, and 88.9% of studies described intervention instructions. Self-recording and self-monitoring were detected in 55.5% of the studies, and monitoring outcomes with patient feedback were reported in 33.3%. Pain reduction due to distraction was observed in 44.4% of the studies while practicing specific tasks to improve performance was found in 22.2%.

Conclusions: This scoping review explored using BCTs within VR-based rehabilitation following TKA. The review revealed that most studies emphasized clinical outcomes without explicitly mentioning the employed BCTs. We employed a triangulation approach to address this gap, combining Felsberg's method, Michie's BCTs Taxonomy, and our knowledge gained from the BCT workshop. This allowed us to identify VR components, mechanisms of action, and relevant keywords for coding BCTs within the interventions.

The findings from this review revealed that specific BCTs, such as instruction and feedback, were commonly integrated into VR-based interventions, whereas others, like self-reward, were less frequently employed. This underscores the significance of considering both the VR components and BCTs in designing effective rehabilitation programs for TKA patients. Future research should prioritize the identification of the most effective BCTs for VR-based rehabilitation, explore the integration of technology, assess the role of healthcare providers, and investigate diverse patient populations to tailor rehabilitation programs more effectively. These efforts aim to enhance the development and adoption of efficient post-TKA rehabilitation programs, ultimately contributing to improved patient recovery and overall well-being.

Keywords: rehabilitation, VR-based rehabilitation, total knee arthroplasty, rehabilitation, telerehabilitation, functional outcomes, Behavior Change Techniques, adherence, and patient perception.

1. INTRODUCTION

Knee osteoarthritis (OA) is one of the most common degenerative joint disorders [1], with a pooled global prevalence of 22.9% after the age of 40 [2], and it is more common in females than males [3]. Knee OA can manifest as primary or secondary, resulting from inflammatory diseases or post-traumatic events [4]. Approximately 654.1 million individuals (over 40 years old) were diagnosed with knee OA in 2020 worldwide [2]. In advanced stages of knee OA, when an individual experiences severe pain and limitation of movement, surgical interventions such as osteotomy and joint replacement or Total Knee Arthroplasty (TKA) are recommended [5], [6]. Every year, more than 50,000 cases of TKA are performed in Canada [7]. In the United States, this is estimated to be about 800,000 cases annually, and it is expected to increase to 3.48 million by 2030 [8].

Although TKA improves function and decreases symptoms, a study by Alrawashdeh (2021) demonstrated that the strength of the quadriceps muscle can decline by approximately 30.9% immediately following TKA [9] and further deteriorate by 50-60% within one month [9]. Therefore, an appropriate rehabilitation program, including motor function training [10] after TKA, can enhance recovery [11].

Rehabilitation following TKA can be performed at the hospital or rehabilitation centers or home-based (domiciliary) under the supervision of therapists. Several studies provide evidence to support that home-based rehabilitation is comparable to hospital-based rehabilitation in improving functional outcomes [12]– [16]. Home-based rehabilitation is favored for its convenience, cost-effectiveness, and time-saving benefits [12]– [16]. Rehabilitation services can be delivered remotely through a diverse range of virtual tools, such as video conferencing, telephone, SMS services, mobile applications, and websites [17], as well as virtual environments (e.g., Augmented Reality and Virtual Reality), gaming technology, and other consoles (such as Nintendo Wii) to improve an individual's functional capabilities [18], [19].

Virtual reality (VR) is an artificial environment that integrates sensory information, typically visual and auditory, enabling the emergence of natural behaviors [20]. VR has been extensively employed in therapeutic programs targeting a range of conditions such as PTSD, anxiety, phobias, schizophrenia, ADHD, autism, and pain management [20]. The use of VR in rehabilitating individuals after TKA has been growing in recent years [21]. In TKA rehabilitation, VR interventions can assume various forms, from non-immersive to fully immersive experiences, with ongoing technological advancements shaping the field [22]. By modifying VR components such as visual field continuity, interactivity, feedback, narrative engagement, user freedom, and visual conformity, we can enhance the level of immersion in VR experiences [19]. These technological advancements have positioned VR as a potential tool for improving physical rehabilitation interventions and outcomes in individuals recovering from TKA [19].

Several systematic reviews have assessed the effect of VR-based rehabilitation on functional outcomes in individuals with TKA [21], [23]– [26]. These reviews have indicated no

significant difference in functional outcomes between VR-based and in-person rehabilitation and may achieve comparable functional outcomes to in-person rehabilitation. These findings suggest that VR-based rehabilitation may have the potential to be an alternative or complement to in-person rehabilitation, offering additional benefits such as increased engagement and motivation in the rehabilitation process [21], [23]– [26].

To realize the effect of VR in rehabilitation, it is necessary to clarify VR components. Felsberg's study [27] presented crucial components to create an ideally stimulating and optimally engaging VR task. These components encompass adaptability, feedback mechanisms, task-oriented goals, interactivity, and competition. These five components are recommended in the design of VR applications for motor rehabilitation. These components encourage people to stay engaged and committed to their exercises [27].

To understand the success of interventions, more is needed to know what works. It's equally important to understand how these interventions work and the mechanisms that explain why they have an effect and can change behavior [28]. Therefore, understanding behavior change during an intervention plays a significant role in answering these questions [28]. Behavior Change Techniques (BCTs) are observable and replicable components of an intervention to modify behavior [29]. In 2013, Michie et al. introduced the BCT Taxonomy (v1) (Table 5), which hierarchically classified 93 techniques into 16 groups [30]. This taxonomy is a plausible method to help address the problem. Analyzing the BCTs enables synthesizing and comparing evidence to customize the interventions based on individual needs, ultimately optimizing outcomes [31].

The BCT Taxonomy has evolved based on theories like social cognitive and planned behavior [32]. It simplifies the comprehension of BCTs by presenting a standardized list, aiding

in selecting the most suitable BCTs for specific objectives [33]. The taxonomy also facilitates the identification and integration of complementary techniques, enabling practitioners to address various facets of behavior change. It becomes easier to tailor interventions for individuals or groups [31]. Moreover, taxonomy serves as a valuable tool for documenting the BCTs employed in interventions and as an educational resource for training. When it comes to designing new interventions, taxonomy proves beneficial. It also improves existing interventions by incorporating more effective BCTs [34]. Beyond this, taxonomy encourages knowledge sharing and promotes evidence-based practice by helping practitioners choose BCTs with established effectiveness in specific contexts. Additionally, it fosters collaboration among researchers [35].

Hence, comprehension of BCTs integration within VR-based rehabilitation programs is necessary to enhance program performance. Exploring studies in this review is imperative to identify these BCTs. When information regarding the BCTs used in a study is readily available, their identification is straightforward. However, in cases where such information is absent, a novel approach is necessary to uncover these BCTs, even when not explicitly mentioned in the study.

The examination of eligible studies within this scoping review revealed that many studies primarily focused on clinical outcomes and did not provide descriptions of the BCTs employed. The rationale for conducting a scoping review to explore BCTs in VR-based interventions following TKA is rooted in the need for a more precise definition regarding used BCTs within the literature of this review. Despite the growing interest in VR-based rehabilitation for individuals undergoing TKA, a significant dearth of comprehensive insights into the specific BCTs integrated within these interventions exist that underscores the need to systematically examine and understand the role of BCTs in enhancing the efficacy of VR-based post-TKA.

Hence, in this study, we endeavored to develop an evidence-based approach for identifying BCTs employed within interventions, particularly in cases where studies lack explicit descriptions.

We employed a triangulation approach that combined Felsberg's method [27], Michie BCTs Taxonomy [32], and insights from a BCTs workshop to establish the study's objectives. The study's objectives are outlined as follows:

Objectives

- 1- To describe the individual components of each VR-based intervention.
- 2- To code and analyze the state of BCTs in VR-based rehabilitation after TKA.

2. METHODS

Protocol Design

The scoping review was implemented in five stages based on Arksey and O'Malley's framework, including (1) identifying the research questions, (2) identifying relevant studies, (3) selecting the studies, (4) charting the data; (5) collating, summarizing, and reporting the results [36].

2.1. Stage 1: Identifying Research Questions

The scoping review focused on the following research questions:

- 1- What components of each VR-based rehabilitation intervention are used for TKA patients?
- 2- Can the components of each intervention be coded to identify the BCTs employed?

2.2. Stage 2: Identifying Relevant Studies.

2.2.1. Search Strategy:

The following search strategy was applied to identify relevant studies:

Four electronic databases were searched: PubMed, Medline (Ovid), CINAHL, and Embase (Ovid). The search used a combination of keywords and MeSH terms, including "total knee replacement" or "total knee arthroplasty," and "virtual reality" or "augmented reality," "immersive technology" or "virtual rehabilitation, remote rehabilitation," and "rehabilitation" or "exercise therapy" or "muscle stretching exercises" or "plyometric exercise" or "resistance training," as well as "health behavior" or "treatment adherence and compliance" or "patient acceptance of health care" or "patient compliance" or "patient participation" or "patient satisfaction" or "patient preference" or "treatment refusal," "behavior change," "behavior change techniques," "functional outcomes," and "innovation development." In addition, the bibliographic references of included articles were manually searched for additional relevant studies.

2.3. Stage 3: Selecting Studies

Based on eligibility criteria, the formal search was done in four steps: 1- articles identification to search by titles, 2- articles screening of titles and abstracts, 3- full-text review of screened articles, 4- selection for final review and organization based on research questions fields.

2.3.1. Inclusion criteria:

2.3.1.1. Participants: Individuals who have undergone TKA receiving VR-based rehabilitation. Participants aged 19 or older who have undergone primary TKA are physically stable with no severe medical illness and possess adequate visual and auditory acuity.

2.3.1.2. Context: The context of the study involves VR-based platforms specifically designed for individuals with TKA. This may include interventions conducted at home.

2.3.1.3. The phenomenon of Interest: This study focuses on the potential BCTs employed in VR-based rehabilitation after TKA.

2.3.1.4. Study Design: Randomized controlled trials (RCTs) and non-randomized controlled trials (non-RCTs) were included in this review.

2.3.1.5. Others: The language of the included articles was limited to English, and studies published from 2010 to 2023 were considered. This time frame was selected because this technology grew mainly during this period [37].

2.3.2. Exclusion criteria:

2.3.2.1. Individuals with claustrophobia, agoraphobia, and psychotic disorders.

2.3.2. 2. Cognitive disorders, history of motion sickness, neurological and vestibular impairments.

2.3.2.3. Revision cases of TKA.

2.3.2.4. Review articles, case studies, and textbooks were excluded from this review.

The searched articles from the database were imported into the Covidence managing search software (2023), and duplicated articles were removed. Two independent reviewers

(Farzad Ravari and Sarah Park) reviewed the titles and abstracts of the remaining articles based on the eligibility criteria. The same reviewers then reviewed the full text of the selected articles to choose appropriate articles for the final scoping review and identify relevant keywords and code BCTs in the studies. Any conflicts between reviewers were resolved through discussion.

The search process is presented in a PRISMA flowchart; all excluded studies' reasons for exclusion were recorded (Table 1). Therefore, 1,455 studies were initially screened from four databases: PubMed, Medline (Ovid), CINAHL, and Embase (Ovid). After eliminating duplicated and irrelevant studies, two independent reviewers examined the complete texts of 117 studies. Among these, 26 studies explored different modes of rehabilitation delivery, and ultimately, nine studies focused on VR-based rehabilitation were incorporated into this scoping review (Table 1).

2.4. Stage 4: Charting the Data

Relevant data were extracted and charted. The information extracted included author(s), year of publication, country, purpose, methods, sample population, intervention type, dose, delivery methods, results, and types of BCTs used in the studies.

2.5. Stage 5: Collating, Summarizing, and Reporting the Results

Understanding BCTs is crucial in psychology and healthcare. However, linking them systematically to the mechanisms of action is challenging [38]. This linkage is essential for accumulating evidence on how BCTs work, explaining when, why, and how behavior change occurs, and proposing mechanisms and moderators of change [38].

We employed observation and inference-based methodology to identify the used BCTs in the studies. Since the selected studies did not explicitly mention the BCTs employed in their interventions, we thoroughly reviewed the details of each study. We aimed to find clues or

descriptions of intervention components that might indicate the presence of any relevant keywords to specific potential BCTs.

The reasoning for conducting this scoping review on exploring BCTs in VR-based rehabilitation after TKA is grounded in uncovering potentially employed BCTs even when they are not explicitly mentioned in the studies. This approach leverages knowledge gained from BCT workshops, emphasizing the reliability of BCT Taxonomy v1 (BCTTv1) (Table 5) and aligning with Felsberg's method to specify and interpret the active elements of behavior-change in interventions [27], [33], [38], [39].

The process systematically investigates the study's objectives, methodology, and interventions. By scrutinizing intervention descriptions and focusing on specific keywords, such as "establish objectives," "define targets," or "set goals," potential BCTs related to goal setting can be inferred [33], [38], [39]. Similarly, terms like "provide feedback," "receive feedback," or "feedback mechanism" suggest the potential integration of BCTs centered around feedback. Additionally, phrases like "reward," "incentive," "prize," or "positive reinforcement" may indicate the inclusion of BCTs related to rewards and incentives. Other cues, such as "offer guidance," "provide instructions," or "offer directions," imply potential BCTs involving the delivery of clear instructions [33], [38], [39]. Keywords like "reflect on progress," "analyze outcomes," or "review achievements" may hint at the application of BCTs involving self-reflection and review. Finally, terms such as "solve challenges," "overcome difficulties," or "address obstacles" could suggest the presence of BCTs focused on problem-solving strategies [33], [38], [39].

Furthermore, Felsberg's methodology[27] offers an approach for identifying critical VR components within VR-based intervention, including adaptability, explicit feedback, task goals,

interactivity, and competition. Linking these VR components with potential BCTs provides insights into the BCTs used in the studies. Moreover, Michie's methodology [38] outlines the coding of BCTs and their mechanisms of action within interventions. This approach helps identify how BCTs are hypothesized to influence behavior through mechanisms of action, categorizing the explicitness of these links as either requiring inference or being explicitly stated.

This scoping review aims to identify BCTs used within interventions based on Felsberg's method and Michie's BCTs Taxonomy [27], [38]. The BCTs workshop experience enhanced our ability to identify keywords in the studies, leading to a comprehensive investigation to reveal the BCTs applied in the reviewed studies. This triangulation approach contributes to a deeper comprehension of exploring BCTs in the studies of this review [33], [38], [39].

3. RESULTS

The search process is presented in a PRISMA flowchart (Table 1), with 1455 studies identified initially. After removing duplicated and irrelevant studies, 117 were assessed for eligibility. Among these, 26 studies explored different modes of rehabilitation delivery, and ultimately, nine studies focused on VR-based rehabilitation were included in this scoping review.

The study participants' age range was from 51 to 81 years, with a mean age of 64.7 years, and 54.3% of the participants were females.

3.1. Description of included studies:

3.1.1. Description of included studies based on publication year.

15% of the studies were published between 2010 and 2015 [40]–[43]. 58% of the studies were published between 2016 and 2020 [12], [43]– [56]. 19% of the studies were published after 2021 [13], [15], [57]– [59] (Fig. 1).

3.1.2. Description of included studies based on country.

Two studies were conducted in the USA [12], [47]. Two studies in Italy [55], [60]. One study was conducted in each of the countries, including Israel [61], China [62], Lebanon [57], South Korea [43], and Spain [42] (Fig. 1).

3.1.3. Description of included studies based on study design.

Seven studies were randomized controlled trials (RCTs) [12], [55], [57], [60], [61], [63], [64], and two were non-randomized controlled trials (N-RCTs) [47], [65].

3.1.4. Description of included studies (VR-based Rehabilitation).

Our investigation focused on VR-based rehabilitation as the primary intervention of interest. Most reviewed studies integrated the VR systems into patients' homes, incorporating motion-tracking sensors and a 3D avatar as a digitally simulated coach. This VR rehabilitation program was conducted under the supervision of a therapist. The intervention typically commenced following the patient's discharge from the hospital. The frequency and duration of these VR-based rehabilitation sessions were flexible and contingent upon each patient's capacity, usually 2 to 6 weeks post-surgery. Consequently, most recorded outcome measures were captured at three specific time points: discharge and the 2nd and 6th weeks post-surgery. Notably, this scoping review identified nine studies that employed VR-based rehabilitation in their interventions [12], [42], [43], [47], [54], [55], [57], [61], [62] (Fig. 1).

3.2.1. Description of studies based on Potential BCTs

We observed no explicit references to the employed BCTs when we explored the VR-based rehabilitation studies [12], [42], [43], [47], [54], [55], [57], [61], [62] that met our inclusion criteria. Furthermore, exploring included VR-based rehabilitation studies in this review [12], [42], [43], [47], [54], [55], [57], [61], [62] revealed these studies mainly emphasized clinical outcomes.

4. DISCUSSION

In this scoping review, we aim to explore used BCTs in VR-based rehabilitation following TKA. The studies were selected based on eligibility criteria and employed VR-based rehabilitation after TKA. A detailed examination of the methodologies and interventions described within these studies revealed an interesting pattern: These studies predominantly focused on clinical outcomes without explicitly describing BCTs. Although lacking direct mention of BCTs, they included specific keywords within their methodologies and interventions.

The question arises regarding identifying potential BCTs in an intervention with no explicit description in the study. Given the inherent requirement in scoping reviews to explore the presence of BCTs even without clear explanations, our approach encompassed the integration of Felsberg's method, Michie's BCTs Taxonomy, and our collective expertise gleaned from BCT workshops. This triangulation approach involved applying Felsberg's methodology [27] to identify VR components, using Michie's BCTs Taxonomy [32] to comprehend the mechanism of action and experience gained through the BCTs workshop to find relevant keywords within studies. Ultimately, link these components to code BCTs.

Felsberg et al. (2019) described crucial VR components that enhance user immersion. These components encompass factors such as the continuity of the visual environment, the level of interactivity, the type and depth of feedback provided, the engagement, the degree of user freedom, and the consistency of visual elements [27]. The components play an essential role in facilitating effective rehabilitation interventions. Each VR component serves a specific purpose, contributing to the overall success of behavior change strategies and fostering a more engaging and motivating rehabilitation experience.

Specific VR components, like interactivity and user freedom, can be connected to shaping knowledge, repetition, and substitution, as well as rewards and threats within the BCTs Taxonomy. Meanwhile, the level and type of feedback can be associated with goal setting and planning, along with feedback and monitoring. Engagement and adherence to visual conformity can be tied to the antecedent within the BCTs Taxonomy.

The findings of this scoping review yielded several remarkable observations. It became evident that specific BCTs, notably "instruction on how to use," "monitoring with feedback," "goal setting and planning," "self-monitoring," and "distraction," were consistently integrated into VR-based rehabilitation interventions. This finding is consistent with a study by Eisele et al. (2019) [66] that found the most common BCTs to enhance adherence to the intervention were goal setting, self-monitoring, and feedback. In contrast, BCTs such as "self-reward" and "material reward" exhibited less frequent use within VR-based rehabilitation programs designed for individuals recovering from TKA. This finding aligns with the study of Willett et al. (2019) [67], which presented that "reward" can enhance adherence in the short term but, in a long time, is not adequate. Other BCTs, such as "natural consequences" and "comparison of behavior," were rarely identified in VR-based interventions. A study by Arigo et al. (2020) [68] presented

that the effect of behavior comparison depends on a person's perception of a goal. This comparison can cause anxiety and decrease motivation.

The table below offers a comprehensive overview of the potential BCTs identified in the studies of this review. These BCTs have been categorized and analyzed according to Michie's BCTs Taxonomy v1, allowing for a systematic exploration of their presence and relevance within the research.

1-Goal & Planning			2- Feedback & Monitoring			3- Social Support		4- Shaping Knowledge	5- Natural Consequences		
1.3- Goal setting (outcome)	1.2- Problem Solving	1.9- Commitment	2.4- Self Monitoring outcome	2.5- Monitoring without feedback	2.7- Monitoring with feedback	3.3- Emotional	3.2- Practical	4.1- Instruction how to perform the behavior	5.1- Health	5.3- environment	5.4- Emotional
Bettger		Bettger	Bettger		Bettger			Bettger			
			Gianola		Gianola			Gianola			
Jin			Jin	Jin				Jin			
Pournajaf					Pournajaf			Pournajaf			
Piqueras			Piqueras	Piqueras				Piqueras			
Lee				Lee							Lee
		Fluet		Fluet				Fluet			
		Reily		Reily		Reily		Reily			
			Fuch	Fuch				Fuch			
6- Comparison of behavior		8- Repetition & Substitution		9- Comparison of outcomes		10- Reward & threat			12- antecedents		
6.1- Demonstration of Behavior	6.2- Social Comparison	8.1- Behavior practice	8.7- Graded Task	9.1- credible source	9.2- Pros & Cons	10.2- Material reward	10.9- Self reward	10.10 Reward (outcome)	12.1- Restructure of physical environment	12.4- Distraction	
						Bettger				Bettger	
		Jin								Jin	
							Pournajaf				
					Piqueras					Piqueras	
		Lee								Lee	
						Reily					

The table below illustrates a selection of potential BCTs that could be identified in the interventions discussed in this review, according to Michie et al.'s (2013) taxonomy (v1) [30].

BCTs Codes	BCTs	Studies
Code 4.1	Shaping the knowledge: Instruction on how to perform the behavior	[12], [42], [44], [47], [55], [57], [60], [61]

Codes 1.1, 1.3	Goal and planning: Goal setting for behavior and outcomes	[12], [60], [63], [64]
Code 2.4	Feedback and monitoring: Self-monitoring of outcomes (using patient-reported outcome measures such as WOMAC, the Patient-Reported Outcomes Measurement System (PROMS))	[12], [55], [63], [69], [70]
Codes 2.5, 2.7	Feedback and monitoring: Monitoring of outcomes with/ without feedback	[47], [55], [57], [60], [61], [63], [64], [70], [71]
Code 12.4	Antecedents: Distraction; attributed pain reduction to psychological distraction in a virtual environment	[12], [63], [64], [72]
Code 1.9	Goal and Planning: Commitment; Adherence to the treatment	[12], [47], [57]
Code 8.1	Repetition and substitution: Behavior practice/rehearsal; practice to become accustomed to the remote rehabilitation system and improve their performance	[63], [65]
Codes 10.2, 10.9	Reward and threat: Material reward, Self-reward; drawn to remote rehabilitation due to its reduced cost and convenient facility.	[12], [57], [60]

The graph below displays the percentage of potentially employed BCTs in the interventions.

The following statements provide specific information on the potential BCTs that might be employed in several studies of this review.

Self-monitoring is a BCTs that involves patients tracking their progress toward a specific goal or behavior. Through self-monitoring, patients better understand their abilities and limitations, enabling them to identify challenges and adjust their behavior accordingly [32]. While self-monitoring is valuable, including external monitoring can yield more reliable outcomes as it guides the improvement process. Monitoring with feedback can significantly impact behavior change within shorter timeframes [32].

Distraction techniques are BCTs that can reduce anxiety and pain, leading to increased engagement and improved outcomes [31]. These techniques are particularly beneficial in VR-based rehabilitation, where patients may need to engage in challenging or uncomfortable exercises. Goal setting and commitment are essential BCTs that enhance adherence to a program, improve outcomes, and increase patient satisfaction [31].

Providing clear instructions for task performance and using verbal cues and feedback during VR-based rehabilitation have improved functional outcomes [31]. By providing clear instructions and feedback, patients can better understand how to perform tasks correctly, leading to improved outcomes and increased engagement with the rehabilitation program [73].

In the following table, BCTs codes are linked with the corresponding VR components, and a brief explanation is provided for each linkage. This format allows for a clear presentation of the connections between the BCTs and the VR features, making it easier for readers to

understand the application and effectiveness of VR in enhancing BCTs within the context of VR-based rehabilitation.

BCT Code	VR Components	Linkage of BCT Codes to VR Components
Shaping the knowledge: code 4.1	Interactivity and User Freedom	In a VR-based rehabilitation program, users can receive interactive and personalized instructions on performing specific exercises correctly. They can interact with the VR environment, allowing them to practice movements repeatedly until they master the proper technique.
Goal and Planning: Codes 1.1, 1.3	Level and Type of Feedback: Engagement	VR can provide real-time feedback on users' progress toward their goals. Visual representations of progress can be displayed in VR, motivating users to stay committed to their rehabilitation journey. Additionally, incorporating a narrative or story-driven element into the VR experience can increase users' sense of commitment and adherence to the treatment plan.
Feedback and Monitoring: Code 2.4	Level and Type of Feedback: Visual Field Continuity	VR can offer various forms of feedback, such as visual cues and data representation, allowing users to monitor their performance and progress during rehabilitation exercises. The visual field continuity ensures a seamless and continuous feedback display, making the monitoring process more engaging and informative.
Antecedents: Code 12.4	Engagement and Visual Conformity	VR can create immersive and distracting virtual environments that help users focus less on pain and discomfort during rehabilitation. Immersing users in a visually conforming and engaging VR scenario diverts their attention from the pain, leading to potential pain reduction.
Repetition and Substitution: Code 8.1	Interactivity and User Freedom	VR offers a platform for repetitive practice of rehabilitation exercises, allowing users to perform movements and tasks multiple times in a controlled and engaging environment. VR's interactive nature helps users familiarize themselves with the rehabilitation system, improving performance.
Reward and Threat: 10.2, 10.9	Interactivity and User Freedom	VR can incorporate reward systems, such as virtual trophies or achievement badges, to provide material rewards or self-rewards to users based on their performance and progress in the VR-based rehabilitation program. This gamification aspect can attract users to participate in rehabilitation due to the engaging and rewarding nature of the VR experience.

The findings of this study could be highly influential, especially in VR-based rehabilitation following TKA. By acknowledging the subtle incorporation of BCTs in VR interventions, researchers can enhance their comprehension of the fundamental factors that lead to successful behavior change [73]. This increased awareness can lead to more precise and effective research approaches, ultimately pushing forward our scientific understanding and the body of evidence in this specialized field [27].

Recognizing the importance of special BCTs like self-monitoring and goal setting can enable healthcare providers to customize their rehabilitation strategies based on patient's needs. Meanwhile, the individuals responsible for designing and developing VR-based rehabilitation programs significantly influence how research findings are applied [74]. The study underscores the significance of specific components within VR, such as the consistency of the visual environment and the degree of interactivity, in enhancing user engagement and immersion. Designers of VR interventions can shape rehabilitation settings that are more conducive to encouraging behavioral changes and improving rehabilitation outcomes, thereby magnifying the influence of their innovations [38].

From a patient-centered perspective, this study's implications are profound and align more closely with each patient's needs and preferences, can enhance the patient's rehabilitation experience, promote greater adherence to rehabilitation, and improve recovery. Incorporating effective BCTs within VR-based rehabilitation programs can result in more cost-effective rehabilitation strategies [31], [73]. Enhanced patient engagement and adherence to interventions can reduce the need for costly, protracted rehabilitation periods, benefiting patients and healthcare systems regarding resource use and overall healthcare costs.

5. CONCLUSION

This scoping review aimed to explore the used BCTs in VR-based rehabilitation after TKA. Exploring VR-based rehabilitation studies within this review showed a lack of clear descriptions regarding BCTs in their methodology and intervention. To identify BCTs in these interventions, we followed Felsberg's method and Michie's BCTs taxonomy to find VR components and mechanisms of action of interventions and, based on our knowledge from the BCTs workshop, find relevant keywords and code BCTs and link to potential BCTs in the interventions.

The findings of this review found that some BCTs, such as "instruction on how to use," "monitoring with feedback," "goal setting and planning," "self-monitoring," and "distraction," were consistently integrated into VR-based rehabilitation interventions. In contrast, BCTs such as "self-reward" and "material reward" were exhibited less frequently. Other BCTs, such as "natural consequences" and "comparison of behavior," were rarely identified in VR-based interventions. These BCTs facilitate the development of personalized and targeted interventions, allowing patients to progress at their own pace and fostering commitment to the rehabilitation process.

The results of this study emphasize the significance of considering both VR components and BCTs in designing and implementing VR-based rehabilitation interventions for TKA patients. Researchers and clinicians can optimize rehabilitation programs by integrating the identified VR components with appropriate BCTs. This scoping review can provide insights into incorporating BCTs in designing VR-based rehabilitation after TKA. Due to the limitations of this study regarding clear descriptions of BCTs in the interventions, more research is required to depict descriptions of BCTs in the future to investigate the role of BCTs in the adoption and performance of VR-based rehabilitation.

6. FUTURE DIRECTION FOR RESEARCH

There are several potential areas for future research; first, the explicit use of BCTs in VR-based rehabilitation after TKA warrants further investigation. Several BCTs have been used in VR-based rehabilitation after TKA, such as goal setting, self-monitoring, and feedback, identifying which BCTs are most effective in promoting adherence to VR-based rehabilitation programs and improving patient outcomes.

The second area of research that could be explored is integrating technology to enhance the use of BCTs in VR-based rehabilitation after TKA. For example, wearable sensors could allow patients to monitor their progress, receive personalized feedback, and connect with healthcare providers for support. Another area for research is examining the role of healthcare providers in delivering BCTs in VR-based rehabilitation after TKA. Studies could investigate what types of providers (e.g., physiotherapists) are most appropriate for VR-based rehabilitation and evaluate the effectiveness of various training approaches for training healthcare providers to incorporate BCTs in VR programs after TKA effectively.

Lastly, exploring VR-based rehabilitation and BCTs after TKA in diverse populations, including older adults, individuals with comorbidities, and those from different cultural backgrounds, could also be an important research direction. Understanding the effectiveness of BCTs in VR-based rehabilitation in these populations can help tailor rehabilitation programs to meet their specific needs and preferences. Future research in these areas can enhance development and broaden the adoption of effective rehabilitation programs after TKA.

7. LIMITATIONS

The present scoping review is characterized by several limitations that demand careful consideration, particularly the role of BCTs within the scope of the studies rather than the effects of VR-based rehabilitation itself. These limitations revolve around the risk of selection bias due to language restrictions, the narrow publication timeframe from 2010 to 2023, and specific weaknesses in the study designs, all imposing significant constraints on the study's findings. Consequently, the review may have missed relevant studies, resulting in an incomplete understanding of how BCTs are used.

Moreover, the studies included in this review exhibit substantial variability in their research design and the characteristics of the interventions. This variance could significantly impact on the reliability and validity of the findings regarding the role of BCTs. Some studies lacked precision in describing their interventions, forcing the reviewers to infer possible BCTs based on each study's methodology. This approach might have yielded different results had the focus and approach of the studies been different.

Additionally, the selected studies encompass various VR-based rehabilitation interventions and involve participants with diverse musculoskeletal conditions. This diversity can make it challenging to draw conclusive insights specifically regarding the role of BCTs. Furthermore, most of these studies had relatively short follow-up periods of up to 12 weeks, which may not adequately capture the long-term impact of BCTs within VR-based rehabilitation.

Lastly, it is crucial to underscore that the available evidence binds the conclusions drawn from this scoping review and may not be universally applicable to all settings or populations. This limitation is a powerful reminder of the pressing need for additional research to elucidate the role of BCTs in VR-based rehabilitation after TKA in diverse populations. Despite these

limitations, this scoping review represents a fundamental starting point for future investigations to uncover BCTs' potential impact and significance in rehabilitation.

Acknowledgments

We want to acknowledge the support and guidance of Ms. Charlotte Beck, Librarian at the University of British Columbia, for her assistance in developing the search strategy and Sara Park, the second reviewer in the study selection by the Covidence.

Funding

N/A

Conflict of Interest

N/A

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APPENDICES

PRISMA 2020 flow diagram for new systematic reviews which included searches of databases, registers and other sources

*Consider, if feasible to do so, reporting the number of records identified from each database or register searched (rather than the total number across all databases/registers).

**If automation tools were used, indicate how many records were excluded by a human and how many were excluded by automation tools.

From: Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, Boutron I, Hoffmann TC, Mulrow CD, et al. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ* 2021;[372](https://doi.org/10.1136/771):n71. doi: 10.1136/771. For more information, visit: <http://www.prisma-statement.org/>

Table 1: PRISMA Flowchart

Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR) Checklist

SECTION	ITEM	PRISMA-ScR CHECKLIST ITEM	REPORTED ON PAGE #
TITLE			
Title	1	Identify the report as a scoping review.	1
ABSTRACT			
Structured summary	2	Provide a structured summary that includes (as applicable): background, objectives, eligibility criteria, sources of evidence, charting methods, results, and conclusions that relate to the review questions and objectives.	2-3
INTRODUCTION			
Rationale	3	Describe the rationale for the review in the context of what is already known. Explain why the review questions/objectives lend themselves to a scoping review approach.	6-7
Objectives	4	Provide an explicit statement of the questions and objectives being addressed with reference to their key elements (e.g., population or participants, concepts, and context) or other relevant key elements used to conceptualize the review questions and/or objectives.	7
METHODS			
Protocol and registration	5	Indicate whether a review protocol exists; state if and where it can be accessed (e.g., a Web address); and if available, provide registration information, including the registration number.	
Eligibility criteria	6	Specify characteristics of the sources of evidence used as eligibility criteria (e.g., years considered, language, and publication status), and provide a rationale.	8-10
Information sources*	7	Describe all information sources in the search (e.g., databases with dates of coverage and contact with authors to identify additional sources), as well as the date the most recent search was executed.	7-8
Search	8	Present the full electronic search strategy for at least 1 database, including any limits used, such that it could be repeated.	9-10
Selection of sources of evidence†	9	State the process for selecting sources of evidence (i.e., screening and eligibility) included in the scoping review.	10-11
Data charting process‡	10	Describe the methods of charting data from the included sources of evidence (e.g., calibrated forms or forms that have been tested by the team before their use, and whether data charting was done independently or in duplicate) and any processes for obtaining and confirming data from investigators.	10
Data items	11	List and define all variables for which data were sought and any assumptions and simplifications made.	11
Critical appraisal of individual sources of evidence§	12	If done, provide a rationale for conducting a critical appraisal of included sources of evidence; describe the methods used and how this information was used in any data synthesis (if appropriate).	11
Synthesis of results	13	Describe the methods of handling and summarizing the data that were charted.	11-16

SECTION	ITEM	PRISMA-ScR CHECKLIST ITEM	REPORTED ON PAGE #
RESULTS			
Selection of sources of evidence	14	Give numbers of sources of evidence screened, assessed for eligibility, and included in the review, with reasons for exclusions at each stage, ideally using a flow diagram.	12-13
Characteristics of sources of evidence	15	For each source of evidence, present characteristics for which data were charted and provide the citations.	11-12
Critical appraisal within sources of evidence	16	If done, present data on critical appraisal of included sources of evidence (see item 12).	N/A
Results of individual sources of evidence	17	For each included source of evidence, present the relevant data that were charted that relate to the review questions and objectives.	11-16
Synthesis of results	18	Summarize and/or present the charting results as they relate to the review questions and objectives.	
DISCUSSION			
Summary of evidence	19	Summarize the main results (including an overview of concepts, themes, and types of evidence available), link to the review questions and objectives, and consider the relevance to key groups.	17-18
Limitations	20	Discuss the limitations of the scoping review process.	21-22
Conclusions	21	Provide a general interpretation of the results with respect to the review questions and objectives, as well as potential implications and/or next steps.	19-20
FUNDING			
Funding	22	Describe sources of funding for the included sources of evidence, as well as sources of funding for the scoping review. Describe the role of the funders of the scoping review.	23

JBI = Joanna Briggs Institute; PRISMA-ScR = Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Reviews.

* Where sources of evidence (see second footnote) are compiled from, such as bibliographic databases, social media platforms, and Web sites.

† A more inclusive/heterogeneous term used to account for the different types of evidence or data sources (e.g., quantitative and/or qualitative research, expert opinion, and policy documents) that may be eligible in a scoping review as opposed to only studies. This is not to be confused with *information sources* (see first footnote).

‡ The frameworks by Arksey and O'Malley (8) and Levac and colleagues (7) and the JBI guidance (4, 5) refer to the process of data extraction in a scoping review as data charting.

§ The process of systematically examining research evidence to assess its validity, results, and relevance before using it to inform a decision. This term is used for items 12 and 19 instead of "risk of bias" (which is more applicable to systematic reviews of interventions) to include and acknowledge the various sources of evidence that may be used in a scoping review (e.g., quantitative and/or qualitative research, expert opinion, and policy document).

From: Tricco AC, Lillie E, Zarin W, O'Brien KK, Colquhoun H, Levac D, et al. PRISMA Extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR): Checklist and Explanation. *Ann Intern Med.* 2018;169:467–473. doi: 10.7326/M18-0850.

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Table 2: PRISMA-ScR Checklist

Fig.1. Publication year and Country

Fig. 2: BCTs used in the studies

Author(s)	Year	Country	Purpose	Methods	Intervention Dose/Delivery	Outcome Measures	Results	BCT
Bettger, J. et al.	2020	USA	Effect of virtual rehabilitation after TKA on cost, safety and functional outcomes	RCTs	N=144, age= 65.4(7.7), Female=59.6%, Virtual exercise rehabilitation assistant (VERA) with 3D avatar, cloud-based. For 12 wks	10m-gait-speed, pain, knee extension, knee flexion, 6MWT, cost	Virtual rehabilitation is effective as traditional rehabilitation in safety, and functional outcomes, virtual rehab has more adherence to treatment, LOS is lesser and Cost is lesser than traditional rehabilitation	1.3: Goal setting & Planning, 1.9: Commitment, 2.4: Self-monitoring, 2.7: Monitoring with Feedback, 4.1: Instruction how to use, 10.2: Material reward, 12.4 Distraction
Chi Jn, et al.	2018	China	Evaluate clinical practicality and benefit of VR for post operation rehabilitation	RCTs	N= 33, male=15(45-45%), female=18(54.55%), age=66.45(3.49), BMI=24.52(2.27), 1st day: dorsiflexion and plantar flexion, 2nd day: row a boat by VR. 30 minutes /3 times daily	WOMAC, VAS, ROM	In the intervention group: WOMAC decreased in 1, 3, and 6 months after TKA, HSS was significantly higher, VAS decreased at 3, 5, and 7 days, and ROM was higher in 3, 7, and 14 days after TKA. The VR-based intervention provides more attraction and motivation by using music and words and causes psychological distraction and perception of pain. VR has 3 important factors: repeatability, feedback, motivation	2.4: Self-monitoring, 2.5: Monitoring without feedback, 4.1: Instruction on how to use, 8.1: Behavior practice, 12.4: Distraction
Fhret, G. et al.	2019	USA	Feasibility of home virtual rehabilitation system (HOVRs)	Pilot study	Enhanced motivation (EM), 20 minutes daily for 12 weeks	Adherence to exercise, Number of sessions of exercise training	Confidence for the feasibility of virtual home rehabilitation, EM improved adherence to exercise, and the number of sessions.	1.9: Commitment, 2.5: Monitoring without feedback, 4.1: Instruction on how to use,

Author(s)	Year	Country	Purpose	Methods	Intervention Dose/ Delivery	Outcome Measures	Results	BCT
Fuch, L. et al.	2022	Israel	Effect of VR on pain and anxiety after TKA	RCTs	N= 30, use VR during rehabilitation	VAS, Anxiety by STAI questionnaire, WOMAC	In the long term: No statistically significant difference between the two groups.	2.4: Self-monitoring, 2.5: Monitoring without feedback, 4.1: Instruction how to use
Gianola, S. et al.	2020	Italy	Compare the efficacy of Early VR-based Rehabilitation after TKA vs traditional rehabilitation	RCTs	N= 35, male= 24(54.5%), age 66.6(8.7), Early VR-based rehabilitation after TKA by VERRS virtual reality rehabilitation system, 60 minutes/5 days	Pain, QOL, Global perceived effect (GPE), Functional outcomes(walking, stair climbing), ROM, Proprioception exercise	VR-based is not superior to the control group in pain relief and other functional outcomes. VR-based only improve proprioception exercise	2.4: Self-monitoring, 2.7: Monitoring with feedback, 4.1: Instruction on how to use
Lee, M. et al.	2016	South Korea	Evaluation of patient perspective and engagement in VR-based rehabilitation (Flow Experience: highly engage)	Mixed Methods	N=25, age= 36.4(14.8), male= 11(44%), BMI= 22.87(2.68), 8 sessions Nintendo+ balance board with some exercise such as Yoga, strength training, balance game, 30 minutes /8 sessions	ROM, muscle strength, Balance, NPRS, LEFS, ABC: activity specific balance confidence, SLS: single leg stance, FSS questionnaire for assessment.	high level of flow experience and therapeutic effect expectation, positive experience on pain perception	2.5: Monitoring without feedback, 5.4: Emotional, 8.1: Behavior Practice, 12.4: Distraction

Author(s)	Year	Country	Purpose	Methods	Intervention Dose/ Delivery	Outcome Measures	Results	BCT
Piqueras, M. et al.	2013	Spain	Effectiveness of interactive virtual rehabilitation (use bio measurement equipment)	single blinded RCTs	N= 65, 3D avatar (wireless sensor), web portal for therapists, 1 hour /10 days, 5 sessions under supervision of therapists, 5 sessions at home	ROM, quadriceps and hamstring muscle strength (Nicholas manual measurement tester NMMT), TUG, VAS, WOMAC	IVT group is effective same as control group	2.4:Self-monitoring, 2.5: Monitoring without feedback, 4.1: Instruction on how to use, 10.9: Self-reward, 12.4: Distraction
Pournajaf, S. et al.	2020	Italy	Balance training by VR-based serious game (SGs)	RCTs	N=29, age=68.31(8.12), male14(48%) BMI 28.51(3.50), Baseline TUG 25.54(9.37), 10MWT 17.08(6.09) VAS 5.26(2.41), VR-based SGs, 45 minutes / 5 sessions weekly/ 3 weeks	TUG, Speed, Walking, Pain, Muscle strength, Balance	No significant difference in the outcome measures between both groups	2.9: Monitoring with feedback, 4.1: Instruction on how to use, 10.9: Self reward
Relly, C. et al.	2021	Lebanon	Evaluation of feasibility and acceptability, cost effectiveness, Effect of VR-based rehabilitation platform	RCTs	VR-Based rehabilitation, age 51.1(15.6), female 6(40%), 1-3 sessions weekly/ 12.5 weeks	feasibility(FIM): easy to use, doable, possible, implementable; acceptability (AIM):	VR-based rehabilitation shows better result in participant' engagement to follow rehabilitation and has better result	1.9: Commitment, 2.5: Monitoring without feedback, 3.3: Emotional support, 4.1: Instruction on how to use, 10.2: Material reward

Table 3: Charted Data on VR-based rehabilitation and BCTs

1-Goal & Planning			2- Feedback & Monitoring			3- Social Support		4- Shaping Knowledge	5- Natural Consequences		
1.3- Goal setting (outcome)	1.2- Problem Solving	1.9- Commitment	2.4- Self Monitoring outcome	2.5- Monitoring without feedback	2.7- Monitoring with feedback	3.3- Emotional	3.2- Practical	4.1- Instruction how to perform the behavior	5.1- Health	5.3- environment	5.4- Emotional
Bettger		Bettger	Bettger		Bettger			Bettger			
			Gianola		Gianola			Gianola			
Jin			Jin	Jin				Jin			
Pournajaf					Pournajaf			Pournajaf			
Piqueras			Piqueras	Piqueras				Piqueras			
Lee				Lee							Lee
		Fhuet		Fhuet				Fhuet			
		Reily		Reily		Reily		Reily			
			Fuch	Fuch				Fuch			
6- Comparison of behavior		8- Repetition & Substitution		9- Comparison of outcomes		10- Reward & threat			12- antecedents		
6.1- Demonstration of Behavior	6.2- Social Comparison	8.1- Behavior practice	8.7- Graded Task	9.1- credible source	9.2- Pros & Cons	10.2- Material reward	10.9- Self reward	10.10 Reward (outcome)	12.1- Restructure of physical environment	12.4- Distraction	
						Bettger				Bettger	
		Jin								Jin	
							Pournajaf				
					Piqueras					Piqueras	
		Lee								Lee	
						Reily					

Table 4: BCTs Used in Studies Chart

BCT Taxonomy (v1): 93 hierarchically-clustered techniques

Page	Grouping and BCTs	Page	Grouping and BCTs	Page	Grouping and BCTs
1	1. Goals and planning	8	6. Comparison of behaviour	16	12. Antecedents
	1.1. Goal setting (behavior) 1.2. Problem solving 1.3. Goal setting (outcome) 1.4. Action planning 1.5. Review behavior goal(s) 1.6. Discrepancy between current behavior and goal 1.7. Review outcome goal(s) 1.8. Behavioral contract 1.9. Commitment		6.1. Demonstration of the behavior 6.2. Social comparison 6.3. Information about others' approval		12.1. Restructuring the physical environment 12.2. Restructuring the social environment 12.3. Avoidance/reducing exposure to cues for the behavior 12.4. Distraction 12.5. Adding objects to the environment 12.6. Body changes
3	2. Feedback and monitoring	9	7. Associations	17	13. Identity
	2.1. Monitoring of behavior by others without feedback 2.2. Feedback on behaviour 2.3. Self-monitoring of behaviour 2.4. Self-monitoring of outcome(s) of behaviour 2.5. Monitoring of outcome(s) of behavior without feedback 2.6. Biofeedback 2.7. Feedback on outcome(s) of behavior		7.1. Prompts/cues 7.2. Cue signalling reward 7.3. Reduce prompts/cues 7.4. Remove access to the reward 7.5. Remove aversive stimulus 7.6. Satiation 7.7. Exposure 7.8. Associative learning		13.1. Identification of self as role model 13.2. Framing/reframing 13.3. Incompatible beliefs 13.4. Valued self-identify 13.5. Identity associated with changed behavior
5	3. Social support	10	8. Repetition and substitution	18	14. Scheduled consequences
	3.1. Social support (unspecified) 3.2. Social support (practical) 3.3. Social support (emotional)		8.1. Behavioral practice/rehearsal 8.2. Behavior substitution 8.3. Habit formation 8.4. Habit reversal 8.5. Overcorrection 8.6. Generalisation of target behavior 8.7. Graded tasks		14.1. Behavior cost 14.2. Punishment 14.3. Remove reward 14.4. Reward approximation 14.5. Rewarding completion 14.6. Situation-specific reward 14.7. Reward incompatible behavior 14.8. Reward alternative behavior 14.9. Reduce reward frequency 14.10. Remove punishment
6	4. Shaping knowledge	11	9. Comparison of outcomes	19	15. Self-belief
	4.1. Instruction on how to perform the behavior 4.2. Information about Antecedents 4.3. Re-attribution 4.4. Behavioral experiments		9.1. Credible source 9.2. Pros and cons 9.3. Comparative imagining of future outcomes		15.1. Verbal persuasion about capability 15.2. Mental rehearsal of successful performance 15.3. Focus on past success 15.4. Self-talk
7	5. Natural consequences	12	10. Reward and threat	19	16. Covert learning
	5.1. Information about health consequences 5.2. Saliency of consequences 5.3. Information about social and environmental consequences 5.4. Monitoring of emotional consequences 5.5. Anticipated regret 5.6. Information about emotional consequences		10.1. Material incentive (behavior) 10.2. Material reward (behavior) 10.3. Non-specific reward 10.4. Social reward 10.5. Social incentive 10.6. Non-specific incentive 10.7. Self-incentive 10.8. Incentive (outcome) 10.9. Self-reward 10.10. Reward (outcome) 10.11. Future punishment		16.1. Imaginary punishment 16.2. Imaginary reward 16.3. Vicarious consequences
		15	11. Regulation		
			11.1. Pharmacological support 11.2. Reduce negative emotions 11.3. Conserving mental resources 11.4. Paradoxical instructions		

Table 5: BCTs Taxonomy V1